

Chemical Examination of *Terminalia bellerica* Roxb. Part I. A New Cardiac Glycoside

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From *Terminalia bellerica* Roxb. a new cardiac glycoside has been isolated. On hydrolysis it yields for each mole of aglycone two moles of d-glucose and one mole of d-galactose. The aglycone is shown chemically and spectroscopically of cardenolide type, containing in the steroidal frame a C-CH₃ group, three hydroxyl groups, and $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated five-membered lactone and a benzene ring.

Terminalia bellerica Roxb. (N. O. Combretaceae), commonly known as 'Bahera' in Hindi, is a large deciduous tree, widely distributed in the plains and lower hills throughout India, Ceylon and Malacca. The composite mixture of the fruits of *T. bellerica*, *T. chebula* and *embelica* known as *TRIPHALA* has been reported^{2,3} to be highly efficacious in the indigenous system of medicine as a laxative, cardiotonic⁴ and in various chronic diseases like piles, dropsy, diarrhoea, biliousness, headache, dyspepsia, ophthalmia, enlarged liver, ascites, etc.

The kernel oil of the belleric fruit has been investigated for its fatty acids and glycerides by Singh and Kumar.⁵ On the pulp of the fruit beyond the mere indication⁶ of the presence of ellagic acid, gallic acid, saponin, tannin and some hygroscopic glycosides, no work has been reported^{2,3} in literature and in view of the reported medicinal properties it was considered of interest to carry out a detailed chemical examination of the extractives from the pulp.

The greyish yellow powder of the dried pulp was first defatted with light petroleum and finally extracted thoroughly with 90% alcohol. The extract on concentration under reduced pressure and fractional precipitation with acetone gave a highly hygroscopic glycoside, m.p. 56°, [α]_D²⁴ -22.7°, which has been provisionally named as *Bellericanin*. Alongwith this glycoside a solid substance possessing the characteristics of a saponin has also been isolated. However, in this communication only the studies on the glycoside *Bellericanin* are described.

Bellericanin is insoluble in most of the organic solvents like benzene, ether, chloroform, etc. but readily dissolves in alcohol and water. It gives a pale yellow solution with aqueous sodium hydroxide, an intense yellow colour with nitric acid and a deep purple-red colour turning to violet in conc. sulphuric acid. It decolourizes potassium permanganate solution.

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Bellericanin gives the Liebermann, Liebermann-Burchard, Salkowski, Rosenheim and Tschugajeff colour tests⁷ suggesting that the carbon skeleton of the molecule is similar to that of the sterols. It develops a red colour with alkaline sodium nitroprusside (Legal test)⁸, gives an orange-red colour with alkaline picric acid (Baljet reaction)⁹, a blue colour with *m*-dinitrobenzene (Raymond test),¹⁰ and reduces an ammoniacal silver nitrate solution (Tollen's reagent)¹¹ indicating¹² that *bellericanin* is a cardiac active glycoside and contains a $\Delta \alpha\beta$ five-membered lactone ring.

Prolonged acid-hydrolysis of *bellericanin* gives an aglycone and a sugar portion. The latter is found to contain glucose, forming an osazone derivative, m.p. 202° and galactose giving mucic acid, m.p. 209° on oxidation with nitric acid. The presence of glucose and galactose in the sugar moiety has also been confirmed by paper chromatography (R_f values for glucose and galactose being 0.530 and 0.488 respectively).

The aglycone portion was subjected to column chromatography over alumina, yielding a white crystalline substance 'Bellericagenin' $C_{23}H_{28}O_5$, m.p. 149° , $[\alpha]_D^{30} -125^\circ$. It is soluble in ether, chloroform and acetone. It develops a purple colour turning to violet with conc. sulphuric acid. It decolourizes potassium permanganate solution.

Bellericagenin responds to all the aforementioned colour reactions and tests, typical and characteristic of a steroidal nucleus⁷ and of a $\Delta \alpha\beta$ five-membered lactone^{8,12} ring in the molecule. In it three hydroxyl¹³ groups and one five-membered lactone¹⁴ ring have been estimated, thus accounting for all the five oxygen atoms.

FIGURE NO. 1- U-V CURVE OF HYDROCARBON $C_{23}H_{28}$

FIG. 1

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Dehydrogenation of bellericagenin with selenium at 340–50° gives a mixture of hydrocarbon of which only one has so far been isolated in pure form. It melts at 125°, forms a picrate, m.p. 118° and analyses indicate the formula $C_{18}H_{16}$. In its ultraviolet absorption spectrum (Fig. 1) the nature of the curve, the positions and intensities of the absorption maxima (258 $m\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.66; 280 $m\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.17; 287 $m\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.05; 302 $m\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.04) clearly indicate^{15,16} that the compound is a cyclópenteno-phenanthrene type. Thus on the basis of this evidence, bellericagenin belongs to the cardenolide group.

The ultraviolet absorption spectrum (fig. 2) of bellericagenin has a strong band at 218 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.6), specific^{17,18} for a $\Delta^{\alpha\beta}$ five-membered lactone system. The other medium band appears at 277.5 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.3) which leads to the inference from the analogy¹⁹ that it contains a benzenoid ring or a conjugated diene system in the nucleus.

FIGURE NO 2 - U-V CURVE OF BELLERICAGENIN

FIG. 2

FIGURE NO 3 - INFRA RED SPECTRUM OF BELLERICAGENIN

FIG. 3

An infrared spectrum has been recorded (fig. 3) with a Carl Zeiss UR-10 instrument (KBr and NaCl). The spectrum contains strong bands at 5.70 and 7.75 μ , indicative of

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the presence of a lactone $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{C}=\text{O} \\ | \end{array}$ associated in a five-membered ring. An intense band at 12.01μ suggests the presence of a benzene ring. There are several strong bands near 7.65 , and 8.61 and 9.61μ which are characteristic of $-\text{OH}$ grouping. The spectrum also contains a strong band at 7.25μ , specific for $\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ and some strong bands near 12.50 and 15.31μ , which could arise from $\text{C}-\text{H}$ stretching out of plane.

Further work on the constitution of bellericanin and the saponin of *T. bellerica* pulp and on the elucidation of the relation to the cardiacactive compounds is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of Bellericanin—Greyish yellow powder (1 kg.) of the dried pulp of *T. bellerica* fruit was defatted with ether and light petroleum (b.p. $40-60^\circ$) by mechanical shaking for 24 hr. giving a fatty matter (7 g.). The residue was then repeatedly extracted with 90% boiling alcohol in a 5 litre flask and the combined extracts concentrated under reduced pressure to a brown coloured syrup. The latter was taken up in warm water and treated with basic lead acetate. After filtering out the heavy golden precipitate of lead salts of saponins and tannins the excess of the precipitating reagent was eliminated from the filtrate by passing hydrogen sulphide gas and filtering off the lead sulphide precipitate. The filtrate was boiled and simultaneously a current of air was passed through it to remove all traces of hydrogen sulphide gas. The aqueous solution was then concentrated to a semi-solid mass and successively extracted with light petroleum (b.p. $60-80^\circ$) and ether to get rid of any resinous and fatty matter. The semi-solid was taken up in redistilled dry methanol. The methanolic solution was dropped in dry acetone, thoroughly agitated, in a fine stream, and by fractional precipitation different fractions were collected. The first fraction was a pale yellow, highly hygroscopic glycoside. This was purified by redissolving in methyl alcohol and running down in well-stirred acetone column at 15° , yielding (30 g), m.p. 56° ; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{22^\circ} -22.7^\circ$.

Another fraction gave a white substance, saponin, which showed the distinctive property of forming a soapy lather in water.

Hydrolysis of Bellericanin—Bellericanin (20 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 500 ml of 50% aqueous methyl alcohol containing 4% sulphuric acid for 50 hr. After removing methyl alcohol, the hydrolysed solution was thoroughly extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent distilled off yielding a semisolid (2.3 g). This was dissolved in dry ether and chromatographed over alumina, with ether and chloroform as eluants, giving a white crystalline compound, bellericagenin, m.p. 149° ; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{30^\circ} -125^\circ$ (alcohol). (Found: C, 71.35; H, 7.36; mol. wt. 380 (Rast). $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 71.84; H, 7.29% and mol. wt. 384).

Estimated¹⁴ lactone: 20.56 mg. of bellericagenin requires 0.58 cc. of 0.1 *N* potassium hydroxide. Calc. 1 equiv. 0.60 ml.

The number of hydroxyl group was estimated¹³ with a mixture of acetic anhydride and pyridine, 0.522 g. requires 3.9 ml of *N*-potassium hydroxide, giving hydroxyl value 2.8.

After extracting the aglycone portion with ether, the aqueous phase was treated with pure barium carbonate till a pH at 6.00 ± 0.5 was maintained and the precipitated barium sulphate filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to a syrup in vacuo. The syrup was extracted with a minimum quantity of freshly distilled pyridine to remove salts, etc., centrifuged and the last traces of pyridine removed under diminished pressure.

Preparation of Osazone—5 ml of phenyl hydrazine reagent (prepared by dissolving 1 part phenyl hydrazine, 1 part glacial acetic acid and 4 parts of water) were added to a solution of mixed sugars (10%; 5 ml) and the whole mixture was allowed to stand in boiling water for 10 minutes, periodically shaking, when a bulky yellow precipitate separated which on recrystallisation from alcohol melted at 202° (reported²⁰ glucosazone, m.p. 204°).

Oxidation: One gram of mixed sugars was treated with conc. nitric acid (3 ml.) and allowed to stand in boiling water until red fumes were evolved. It was heated at 70° for another 25 minutes, diluted with water and the white precipitate filtered and recrystallized from 50% hot alcohol, m.p. 209° (reported²¹ mucic acid, m.p. 213°).

A 1% solution of mixed sugars was subjected to one-way descending chromatography over Whatman No. 1 filter paper, using butanol-ethanol-water (4:1:5) as solvent. Benzidine was used as a spraying agent. By running standard sugars side by side, the sugars in the mixture were identified as glucose and galactose from their R_f values as 0.530 and 0.488 respectively.

Estimation of Sugars—The sugar spots, separated on the paper chromatogram, were extracted with refluxing of water, 5 ml. in the case of each sugar spot. To this extract Somogyi²² copper reagent (5 ml.) was added and placed in a briskly boiling water-bath for 25 minutes. Potassium iodide solution (2.5%; 5 ml.) was then run down the side of the tube followed by 1.5 ml. of 2 *N* sulphuric acid. The contents were titrated with 0.005 *N* sodium thiosulphate, using starch solution (1%) as an indicator. The mixture was found to contain respectively 0.11 mg. of glucose and 0.058 mg. of galactose, indicating the molecular ratio thereof as 1.8:1.

Dehydrogenation of Bellericagenin—An intimate mixture of bellericagenin (2 g.) and selenium (18 g.) was heated in a sealed tube at $340-50^\circ$ for 48 hr. The contents of the tube were pulverized and extracted with hot benzene. The extract was treated with finely cut sodium metal to remove selenium traces and the solvent distilled off giving a resinous mass which was dissolved in benzene, run down a column of alumina and eluted with ether and chloroform, giving a colourless crystalline substance, which on recrystallization from benzene melted at 126° . Found: C, 92.9; H, 6.9. $C_{18}H_{16}$ requires: C, 93.1; H, 6.8%. It forms a picrate, m.p. 118° .

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